

Is **non-English-language** literature important in science?

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Language barriers to the **global synthesis** of scientific knowledge

Language barriers to the **local application** of scientific knowledge

Language barriers to the **career development** of non-native English speakers

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Language barriers to the synthesis of knowledge

How is **non-English-language science** used in global knowledge syntheses?

On average, **96.6%** of the references cited in eight IPBES assessments was in **English**

Existing conservation literature
(Amano et al 2016)

English	93.3	93.1	98.0	98.0	94.7	100	94.0	96.3	64%
Spanish	3.3	1.3	0.7		5.3			1.4	vs
French	2.0	3.1	1.3	2.0				1.1	36%
Indonesia	0.7							0.1	
Portuguese	0.7	0.6						0.2	
German		0.6					0.7	0.2	
Italian		0.6						0.1	
Russian		0.6					4.7	0.7	
Uzbek							0.7	0.1	

What are the consequences of ignoring **non-English-language science**?

1. Losing access to a non-negligible amount of knowledge

One-third of scientific documents on conservation are written in **languages other than English**

Number of scientific documents on conservation published in 2014 in 16 languages

What are the consequences of ignoring **non-English-language science**?

1. Losing access to a non-negligible amount of knowledge

The number of conservation articles published in non-English languages is increasing

Yearly changes in the number of scientific documents on conservation in 16 languages

What are the consequences of ignoring **non-English-language science**?

2. Causing biases in our understanding

Language bias in evidence synthesis

**Language bias in
*statistical results***

What are the consequences of ignoring **non-English-language science**?

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Language bias in evidence synthesis

What are the consequences of ignoring **non-English-language science**?

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Study location of **English-language** studies testing conservation interventions

What are the consequences of ignoring **non-English-language science**?

2. Causing biases in our understanding

Study location of **English-** vs **non-English-language** studies testing conservation interventions

Use scientific knowledge sourced from **multiple languages**

Working with collaborators who are collectively native speakers of 16 languages

Amano et al (2021) PLOS Biology

Use scientific knowledge sourced from **multiple languages**

List of 466 peer-reviewed non-English-language journals in ecology and conservation

Language	Country/Region	Journal title in English	Journal title in the non-English language	First publication year	Latest publication year	URL
Arabic	Lebanon	Journal of King Abdulaziz University: Environmental Design Science	مجلة جامعة الملك عبد العزيز: علوم تصميم البيئة	2003	2017	https://
Arabic	Lebanon	The Arab Journal for Arid Environments	المجلة العربية للبيئات الجافة	2009	2018	https://
Arabic	Lebanon	Afak Ilmia journal	مجلة آفاق علمية	2017	2020	https://
Arabic	Lebanon	Marsh Bulletin	مجلة الأهوار	2006	2020	https://
Arabic	Lebanon	Journal of Agricultural, Environmental and Veterinary Sciences	مجلة العلوم الزراعية والبيئية والبيطرية	2017	2020	https://
Arabic	Lebanon	Baghdad Science Journal	مجلة بغداد للعلوم	2004	2020	https://
Arabic	Lebanon	Journal of King Abdulaziz University: Economics and Administration	مجلة جامعة الملك عبد العزيز: الاقتصاد والإدارة	1988	2020	https://
Arabic	Lebanon	Journal of King Abdulaziz University: Marine Sciences	مجلة جامعة الملك عبد العزيز: علوم البحار	1990	2018	https://
Arabic	Lebanon	Tishreen University Journal for Research and Scientific Studies - Biology	مجلة تشرين للبحوث والدراسات العلمية - سلسلة العلوم البيولوجية	2001	2020	https://
Arabic	Lebanon	Journal of Marine Sciences and Environmental Techniques	مجلة علوم البحار والتقنيات البيئية	2015	2019	https://
Arabic	Lebanon	Journal of thi-qar science	مجلة علوم ذي قار	2008	2018	https://
Arabic	Lebanon	Journal of Plant Protection	مجلة وقاية النبات العربية	1983	2020	https://
Dutch	Belgium	Mededelingen van de Faculteit Landbouwwetenschappen Universiteit Gent				https://
Dutch	Netherlands	Natuurhistorisch Maandblad				
Finish	Finland	Memoranda Societatis pro Fauna et Flora Fennica				
French	Africa	African Agronomy	Agronomie Africaine	2000	2019	https://
French	Canada	The Canadian Naturalist	Le Naturaliste Canadien	1868	2020	https://
French	France	Alauda	Alauda	1929	2020	https://
French	France	Rural alternatives	Alternatives rurales	2014	2019	https://
French	France	Annals of the national water and forest school and of the research and	Annales de l'école nationale des eaux et forêts et de	1923	1963	https://
French	France	Scientific annals of Limousin	Annales Scientifiques du Limousin	1985	2019	https://
French	France	Biotechnology, Agronomy, Society and Environment	Biotechnologie, Agronomie, Société et Environnement	2004	2020	https://
French	France	Tropical Woodlands and Forests	Bois et Forêts des Tropiques	1947	2020	https://
French	France	Bulletin of the French herpetological society	Bulletin de la société herpétologique de France	1976	2020	https://
French	France	Bulletin of the Vaud Natural Sciences Society	Bulletin de la Société Vaudoise des Sciences Naturelles	1864	2019	https://
French	France	Bulletin of the French zoology Society	Bulletin de la Société zoologique de France	1876	2020	https://
French	France	Bulletin Français de la Pêche et de la Pisciculture				
French	France	Scientific Letters from the regional natural Park of Luberon and the	Courrier scientifique du Parc naturel régional du Lub	1997	2016	http://
French	France	Ecologia mediterranea	Ecologia mediterranea	1975	2020	https://
French	France	Ecological science	Écoscience	2015	2020	https://
French	France	Applied aquatic ecology	Hydroécologie Appliquée	1989	2018	https://
French	France	Earth and life (Revue d'écologie)	La terre et la vie (Revue d'écologie)	1931	2018	https://
French	France	Lambillionea	Lambillionea	1900	2020	https://
French	France	The avocet	L'avocette	1976	2012	https://
French	France	Naturae	Naturae	2017	2020	https://
French	France	Nature Sciences Society	Natures Sciences Sociétés	1993	2019	https://
French	France	Rencontre Recherche Ruminants				
French	France	Revue Étude et Gestion des Sols		1994	2020	https://
French	France	French forestry journal	Revue forestière française	1949	2019	https://
French	France	Water and Land Sciences	Sciences Eaux et Territoires	2010	2020	https://
French	France	Scientific reports of the Vanoise national park	Travaux scientifiques du Parc national de la Vanoise	1970	2009	https://
French	France	Scientific reports of the Port-Cros national park	Travaux Scientifiques du Parc National de Port-Cros	1975	2019	https://

Language-specific literature search system

Language	Database	URL
Spanish	SciELO	https://scielo.org/en
Portuguese	SciELO	https://scielo.org/en
Chinese (Simplified)	CNKI	https://cnki.net/
Chinese (Traditional)	Airiti Library	https://www.airitilibrary.com/
French	Persee	https://www.persee.fr/
German	BASE	https://de.base-search.net/
Japanese	J-Stage	https://www.jstage.ist.go.jp/browse/-char/en
Korean	Korean Citation Index	https://www.kci.go.kr/kciportal/main.kci?locale=en
Polish	Polska Bibliografia	https://pbn.nauka.gov.pl/core/#/home

Chowdhury et al (2021)
Conserv Biol

Box 1. Strategies for and challenges in synthesising non-English-language literature

Searching effectively and understanding non-English-language literature can be a challenging task, with the lack of relevant language skills often being a key reason for excluding non-English-language literature in evidence synthesis [8]. Here, we summarise how we can practically synthesise non-English-language literature under such restrictions.

How to choose languages

Including more languages would make a synthesis more comprehensive, but given that

How can we overcome **language barriers** in science?

Ten tips for overcoming language barriers in science

1. Disseminate research in multiple languages
2. Use scientific knowledge sourced from multiple languages
3. Increase the visibility of non-English-language science
4. Translate scientific terms
5. Provide genuine support to non-native speakers
6. Distinguish language skills from scientific quality
7. Consider language balance in scientific activities
8. Acknowledge efforts to overcome language barriers
9. Be considerate of non-native speakers
10. Make use of existing resources and opportunities

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Amano et al (2016, 2021) PLOS Biology

Amano et al (2022) EcoEvoRxiv

Chowdhury et al (2021) Conserv Biol

Konno et al (2020) Ecology and Evolution

Lynch et al (2021) One Earth